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Short Communication

Real-time monitoring of Ti-Nb-Ta-Zr and commercially pure Ti interaction with H₂O₂ using atomic force microscopy and atomic emission spectroelectrochemistry

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ABSTRACT

This study offers a new approach to analyze surface behavior of titanium biomaterials during their exposure to the H₂O₂-enriched fluid which simulates post-operative inflammatory conditions. In this work *in situ* AFM and AESEC tests were exploited to study the origin of initial inflammatory-induced degradation for commercially pure Ti (CP-Ti) and Ti-29Nb-13Ta-4.6Zr (TNTZ) alloy. Overall results indicate that initial interaction between H₂O₂ and TNTZ surface results only in dissolution of the alloy, while for CP-Ti both oxide formation and dissolution give important contribution to the degradation process. Proposed methodology yields insight into the origin of corrosion properties registered during standard electrochemical tests that are used to evaluate biomaterials.

1. Introduction

Commercially used Ti-based biomaterials have demonstrated a high corrosion resistance in many standard laboratory tests, including those performed according to the accepted ASTM protocol [1]. However, the degradation of these materials in the human body has been confirmed in clinical studies [2–5]. One of the major factors contributing the lower corrosion resistance *in vivo* is the production of aggressive species during periods of acute inflammation, which is a natural and necessary part of body's response to the harsh operative procedure [6]. Inflammatory-induced corrosion in artificial biological fluids has been simulated by the addition of reactive oxygen species (ROS), such as hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂), that are produced by immune cells during their interaction with implant's surface [7–10]. Up to the present time, the effect of inflammatory species on the corrosion phenomena was studied mainly for widely-used Ti-based biomaterials such as commercially pure Ti (CP-Ti) [11–13] or Ti-6Al-4V [7,14–16]. Accelerated corrosion in simulated inflammatory conditions was confirmed by electrochemical tests such electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS). It was found

that the enrichment of simulated body fluid in the H₂O₂ resulted in a significant drop of the oxide layer resistance value, designated from EIS tests [13,17,18].

Interaction between the immune system and a metallic biomaterial's surface can be described as a positive feedback loop, where inflammatory reactions induce corrosion and the corrosion induces further inflammation and so on. For these reasons, it is important to block the initial inflammatory-induced degradation of Ti-based biomaterials to avoid a cascade of undesirable reactions that can accelerate the corrosion process. This can be done by tailoring the chemical composition of titanium-based materials [19]. It was found that one of the vanadium-free titanium biomedical alloy, Ti-29Nb-13Ta-4.6Zr (TNTZ) is less prone to H₂O₂-induced corrosion compared to the CP-Ti [20,21]. TNTZ surface shows unique stability in the inflammatory conditions which was indicated by the low difference between the oxide layer resistance values designated in the phosphate-buffered saline (PBS) and PBS + H₂O₂. Current conclusions related to TNTZ behavior during inflammation are based on the *in situ* electrochemical and immersion tests that are followed by post-immersion X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) or

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focused ion beam combined with transmission electron microscopy (FIB-TEM) studies [19]. However, this approach does not give information related to the kinetics of the processes that contribute to the corrosion of implantable devices, precisely (i) oxide layer growth, and (ii) dissolution. Moreover, removing materials from the tested fluid and characterizing them by microscopy techniques, which requires using high vacuum, undoubtedly changes the hydrated oxide that is formed in the inflammatory environment [22].

These drawbacks can be overcome by exploiting atomic emission spectroelectrochemistry (AESEC) and *in situ* AFM techniques. AESEC monitors the dissolution of the alloying elements during exposure of the tested materials to a fluid *in situ* and in the real-time. In turn, *in situ* AFM gives an opportunity to observe oxide layer changes *in situ* and in the real-time during immersion and provides near atomic level information about the surface evolution in the liquid [22,23]. Both *in situ* AFM and AESEC methods are unexploited in the case of widely investigated vanadium-free titanium biomedical alloys, such as TNTZ [24]. Combining this two techniques gives a possibility to verify if the superior initial oxide layer resistance observed for titanium alloy [20] is related only to the suppressed dissolution or whether less pronounced oxide layer formation also contribute to this phenomenon. Hence, in this study we monitored the initial real-time inflammatory-induced corrosion process of CP-Ti and TNTZ alloy by both *in situ* AFM and AESEC techniques. Moreover, we provided the first evidence of how altering surface features of vanadium-free titanium alloy by its chemical etching influences the mechanism of inflammatory-induced corrosion. Proposed research methodology opens a new avenue for the *in vitro* safety verification of currently under development titanium biomaterials and their surface modification or functionalization.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Materials and solution preparation

CP-Ti and Ti-29Nb-13Ta-4.6Zr (TNTZ) in the recrystallized states were used in this study. Grain sizes designated for tested materials were as follows: (i) CP-Ti: $46 \pm 16 \mu\text{m}$, (ii) TNTZ: $113 \pm 44 \mu\text{m}$ (Fig. 1) Details about fabrication of the tested materials are provided elsewhere [19,20]. Before corrosion tests, samples were ground using SiC abrasive paper with following gradation: #600, #1200, and #2400. The grinding process was followed by polishing with a mixture of colloidal silica suspension with $0.04 \mu\text{m}$ particle size (OP-S, Struers) and H_2O_2 (30 wt% in water, Sigma Aldrich). Part of the samples were then subjected to the chemical etching using Kroll's reagent with following composition: 2 % HF + 4 % HNO_3 + H_2O . The aim of this procedure was to reveal grain

boundaries and to increase nanopopography within the grains. Surface preparation procedures were performed three days before each test. Immediately before measurements, samples were re-polished for one minute and cleaned in isopropanol.

Inflammatory-induced degradation was tested in PBS + H_2O_2 solution which was prepared by dissolving PBS tablet (Sigma Aldrich) in deionized water. Inflammatory fluid *in vivo* contains variety of ROS such as H_2O_2 , HOCl or radicals. However, standard biological fluids (such as PBS) enriched with H_2O_2 are commonly accepted to study inflammatory-induced corrosion as H_2O_2 can act itself as an intermediate compound of reactions that are taking place on biomaterial surface which simulates complex post-operative environment [9–11,25]. Physiological concentration of H_2O_2 that was measured in extracellular environments is reported to be in the μM range [18]. However, it has to be mentioned that locally, H_2O_2 content can reach the mM level (especially within the crevices when the exchanging of the solution is limited) and can, in fact, be generated by reduction reactions at metal electrode surfaces [26]. *In vitro* experiments exploited mostly suprphysiological concentration of H_2O_2 (from 33 mM [18] to 100 mM [7,14]). This approach accelerates corrosion processes leading to a decrease in experimental time necessary to observe possible H_2O_2 -induced degradation [25]. This is important especially for the real-time *in situ* techniques, which requires constant monitoring of experiments. In this study, we decided to use the lowest concentration of H_2O_2 from those mentioned above ($33 \text{ mM} = 0.1 \% \text{ H}_2\text{O}_2$) which is the closest to the realistic conditions and simultaneously gave us a chance to visualize surface changes in reasonable time and to detect titanium dissolution.

2.2. Real-time analysis of the surface evolution in the inflammatory fluid: *in situ* AFM

Surface topography analysis included following steps: (i) AFM scanning in air in order to set the distance between the tip and sample surface, (ii) the addition of an approximate 500 μl droplet of the PBS + 0.1 % H_2O_2 on the sample surface, and (iii) re-engaging the tip in the solution and performing AFM scanning in the solution. AFM measurements were conducted in the direct contact mode using Dimension ICON AFM, Bruker and ScanAsyst Fluid probe. Data visualization and numerical analysis were performed with the NanoScope Analysis, Bruker software.

2.3. Real-time dissolution monitoring in the inflammatory fluid: AESEC

Ion-dissolution monitoring was performed with a flow cell that was combined with an inductively coupled plasma atomic emission

Fig. 1. Microstructure of tested materials visualized using light microscope.

spectrometer (ICP-AES), a Horiba Ultima 2C coupled with a three-electrode electrochemical flow cell with a saturated calomel reference electrode and Pt wire counter electrode. The reference and counter electrodes were separated from the sample by a porous membrane. The flow rate of the tested fluid (PBS + 0.1 % H₂O₂) was 1 ml per minute. Ti emission was measured at the wavelength 337.279 nm. All of the tests were calibrated by conventional methods of ICP-AES analysis using normalized standards. Detection limit for particular elements were as follows: (i) CP-Ti: Ti = 1.9 ppb, (ii) TNTZ: Ti: 1.9 ppb, Nb: 8.3 ppb, Ta: 15.7 ppb, Zr: 3.4 ppb. The elemental dissolution rate (ν_M) was designated according to the mathematical formulas that are presented elsewhere [27]. Electrode potential was monitored with a Gamry Reference 600, Potentiostat/galvanostat.

3. Results

The evolution of the oxide layer morphology was studied by *in situ* AFM

observations conducted for 90 min in the droplet of PBS + H₂O₂ (Fig. 2). For CP-Ti, two groups of the oxide domes could be distinguished: (i) larger oxide domes with few nm in height and c.a. 0.5–1 μm lateral dimension, (ii) smaller oxide domes with a less than 1 nm in height and less than 0.5 μm lateral dimension (Fig. 2). It can be noticed that the larger domes remain almost stable in size during 90 min of immersion. The smaller oxide domes, however, tend to coalesce during immersion, which results in a flattening of the surface. Firstly, oxide domes were formed at the preferred sites of the surface that are characterized by enhanced reactivity (e.g. grain boundaries, impurities, interstitials) and subsequently grew in height up to a critical level. Then, in the surrounding planar regions, smaller domes are created, which resulted in a complete surface coverage after 30 min in PBS + H₂O₂ (Fig. 2). Conversely, no morphological changes in the surface layer were observed for TNTZ during immersion in the PBS + H₂O₂. Based on the topography profiles it can be assumed that the oxide layer formed on TNTZ alloy was stable during the whole immersion period (Fig. 2). This

Fig. 2. Monitoring of the oxide layer changes during immersion of polished CP-Ti and TNTZ in PBS + H₂O₂; *in situ* AFM study. Note the smoothing of the surface oxides over time for CP-Ti and the smooth and non-varying nature of TNTZ surfaces.

indicates that the lattice diffusion of oxygen vacancies and titanium interstitials, which determine the solution growth of titanium oxide layers, is hindered in case of TNTZ alloy.

The differences between the oxide formation processes of CP-Ti and TNTZ in the polished state, may be attributed to the differential chemical compositions of the oxides formed on their surfaces. However, the surfaces of real implantable materials are usually functionalized e.g. by altering their topography in order to stimulate desired biological responses during osseointegration process [28]. A change in surface topography can affect the oxide layer stability during immersion in the fluid, which may affect the kinetics of oxide dome nucleation and growth. To study this phenomenon, *in situ* AFM experiments were repeated for the samples subjected to chemical etching in the mixture of HF and HNO₃ acids (Kroll agent). Fig. 3 illustrates the surface morphology in the vicinity of selected triple point revealed for CP-Ti and TNTZ respectively. AFM micrographs captured in air confirmed that that surface etching in the Kroll agent developed nanoscale roughness within the grain interiors. In case of TNTZ, the etched surface is significantly smoother, which is reflected by a visibly lower value of the arithmetic roughness (R_a) compared to CP-Ti (Fig. 4).

In addition to the presence of lower surface roughness within the grains, the relative difference between the height of grain boundaries

and grain interiors is also significantly lower for TNTZ (Fig. 3). It can be noticed that for CP-Ti, the vertical distance between the lowest and the highest point did not change significantly after its immersion in the fluid (165 nm – distance in air, and 167 nm – distance after 90 min of immersion). This indicates that the kinetics of oxide layer growth in PBS + H₂O₂ (under steady-state conditions) is similar within both grain interiors and grain boundaries (Fig. 3). Contrary conclusions can be derived from the AFM observations performed for the etched TNTZ alloy (Fig. 3). It was found that immediately after immersion, the vertical distance between the highest and the lowest features is reduced for approximately 15 nm, which confirms that for TNTZ alloy oxide layer growth is more pronounced within the area of grain boundaries. For both CP-Ti and TNTZ, rapid nucleation of the oxide domes was observed after their immersion in PBS + H₂O₂ (Fig. 4).

In addition to oxide growth, a major contribution to corrosion is the dissolution of the alloy. The dissolution of Ti was measured directly during immersion in PBS + H₂O₂ using AESEC. Typical dissolution profiles are shown in Fig. 5. The electrolyte came into contact with the sample at $t = 0$ and the dissolution rates and open circuit potential were followed for 1200 s. For $t < 0$ was the background emission due to the electrolyte alone. At $t = 0$, a significant increase of detected Ti ions was visible as a dissolution peak around 0–50 s. After c.a. 200 s, the Ti

Fig. 3. Monitoring of the oxide layer changes during immersion of etched CP-Ti and TNTZ in PBS + H₂O₂; *in situ* AFM study.

Fig. 4. Monitoring of the oxide layer changes within the grain interior of CP-Ti and TNTZ during immersion of etched samples in PBS + H₂O₂: *in situ* AFM study.

Fig. 5. Real-time monitoring of chemical elements dissolution during immersion of (a) CP-Ti and (b), (c) TNTZ in the flowing PBS + H₂O₂ solution.

dissolution rate stabilized for both materials. For both CP-Ti and TNTZ, the Ti signal was detectable during the whole time of AESEC analysis at the steady-state conditions (Fig. 5). In order to compare the amount of Ti ions dissolved into the fluid from tested materials, the average value of the dissolution rate was calculated based the data between 200 s and 1200 s. Single high peaks detected for CP-Ti c.a. at 400 s and for TNTZ c. a. 700 s were not included in the calculations (Fig. 5). Average dissolution rate of CP-Ti was calculated as $64 \text{ pg} \cdot \text{cm}^{-2} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$, while for TNTZ alloy the value was found to be c.a. 2.4 times lower ($27 \text{ pg} \cdot \text{cm}^{-2} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$). Note that considering stoichiometry of TNTZ (Ti content 53.4 wt%) AESEC results revealed that dissolution of Ti in TNTZ was suppressed compared to CP-Ti. Contrary to Ti, the dissolution of alloying elements in TNTZ alloy (Nb, Ta, and Zr) was below the detection limit. Apart from

the higher dissolution rate, the more substantial change in OCP value was observed for CP-Ti (Fig. 5).

4. Discussion

By combining *in situ* AFM and AESEC analysis, oxide film formation and dissolution phenomena could be distinguished during the corrosion of the standard CP-Ti and the relatively novel vanadium-free titanium alloy (TNTZ). Consequently, the proposed methodology provides an opportunity to understand the origin of differences between CP-Ti and TNTZ corrosion behavior that were found based on the standard electrochemical tests performed in the simulated inflammatory fluid. AFM experiments revealed that oxide layer formed on the CP-Ti surface is

rebuilt rapidly after its contact with PBS + H₂O₂, which is reflected in the nucleation of oxide domes. When the nanometric, air-formed oxide layer is exposed to the fluid, ions and electrons diffuse across the oxide which results in its evolution [29]. Transfer of Ti ions across the film introduces tensile stresses at the Ti/oxide boundary, which consequently results in the formation of the oxide domes as can be seen from the AFM micrographs captured after 30 min of immersion (Fig. 2). With the increase of immersion time adjacent oxide domes tend to coalesce which should suppress the ion transport across the oxide. This can be responsible for the significant enhancement of corrosion resistance which was observed for CP-Ti after a long term (24 h) immersion in the PBS + H₂O₂ [13]. However, despite surface smoothening, nucleation of the new oxide domes was observed after 90 min of CP-Ti immersion (Fig. 2). The constant formation of the oxide domes in simulated inflammatory body fluid explain the increase of titanium oxide layer thickness up to several dozens of nm after a few years of exposure to the human body conditions [30]. Nucleation and further coalescence of the oxide domes in PBS + H₂O₂ is in agreement with previous research performed for CP-Ti tested in the standard PBS solution [22].

Contrary to CP-Ti, no inflammatory-induced morphological changes were detected for polished TNTZ during its 90 min of exposure to the PBS + H₂O₂ (Fig. 2). Both tested materials were mirror-like polished and demonstrated the same type of recrystallized structure, which consist of defect-free micrometric grains [13,19]. For this reason, it can be assumed that suppressed oxide growth for TNTZ alloy is strictly related to the complex chemical composition of the native oxide layer formed on its surface. Indeed, previous post-immersion XPS studies revealed that unique behavior of TNTZ can be related to the presence of Zr in the bulk alloy and thereby ZrO₂ on its surface [19]. It was found that the transformation from Zr to ZrO₂ is preferential during long-term of TNTZ exposure to the PBS + H₂O₂ solution [19]. This can be related to the slightly lower oxide formation energy for ZrO₂ (−1100.6 kJ/mol) [31] compared to the TiO₂ (−992 kJ/mol) [32]. Results obtained for binary Ti-Zr alloy indicate that contrary to Ti and TiO₂, Zr and ZrO₂ are not prone to form the complex compounds with H₂O₂ [15]. Unique stability of ZrO₂ in the biological fluid can be associated with higher dissociation energy for Zr-O bonds (766 kJ/mol) than for Ti-O bonds (666 kJ/mol) [33]. High strength of Zr-O bonds can prevents ZrO₂ disruption in H₂O₂-rich solution. Findings related to the beneficial role of Zr on the suppression of H₂O₂-induced degradation were confirmed by gradually decreasing susceptibility to corrosion with the increasing content of Zr in binary Ti-Zr alloys. It was found that increasing of Zr concentration in Ti-Zr alloys resulted in the reduction of OCP value which can be related to suppression of cathodic reactions [15]. Finally, it has to be mentioned that ZrO₂ act as a catalyzer for H₂O₂ decomposition [34]. This can possibly result in a rapid decrease of H₂O₂ content in PBS surrounded TNTZ alloy, making testing fluid less aggressive. Consequently, the presence of ZrO₂ in TNTZ oxide layer could partially block the H₂O₂-induced transformation of TiO₂ oxide, which could be the reason for the lack of morphological changes observed for TNTZ during short, 90 min *in situ* AFM observations. It can be concluded that short-term *in situ* AFM experiments performed for the mirror-like TNTZ surface, did not allow to observe any morphological changes that can help to understand the process of the inflammatory-induced evolution of the oxide film. Gaining this knowledge was possible by performing *in situ* AFM tests for the chemically treated materials. These experiments revealed that TNTZ oxide film growth follows a similar mechanism as was observed for CP-Ti, which involves the nucleation of the oxide domes and their further coalescence, ultimately leading to surface smoothening (Fig. 4).

Apart from suppressed H₂O₂-induced oxide growth, TNTZ alloy also demonstrated a lower tendency to dissolution in the inflammatory fluid compared to the standard CP-Ti. AESEC measurements revealed that the dissolution rate of elemental Ti was c.a. 2.4 times lower for TNTZ alloy. It should be kept in mind that a mass content of Ti in tested TNTZ material exceeded 50 %, which indicates that dissolution rate of this element should not be lower than 2 times compared to the CP-Ti.

Moreover, the dissolution of the alloying elements in TNTZ (Nb, Ta, and Zr) was under their respective detection limit. However, considering the overall results of both *in situ* AFM and AESEC analysis, it can be concluded that the initial, inflammatory-induced corrosion process of TNTZ alloy is associated rather with the dissolution of Ti. Oxide layer growth does not participate directly in the corrosion phenomena in the simulated inflammatory fluid.

5. Conclusions

This work presents a new approach to biomaterials testing that permits *in situ* monitoring of both dissolution and oxide layer growth phenomena that contribute to the overall corrosion process. Application of this methodology offers insight into the origin of corrosion behavior detected during standard electrochemical tests, such as EIS, that are commonly used for evaluating functional properties of newly designed biomaterials. Moreover, this study provides the first evidence that at the steady-state conditions, as can be found in the human body, noticeable dissolution occur for both CP-Ti and TNTZ alloy immediately after their immersion in simulated inflammatory fluid (PBS + H₂O₂). Combining *in situ* AFM and AESEC results demonstrates that the H₂O₂-induced corrosion processes involve both dissolution and oxide growth for CP-Ti, while dissolution is the major contribution for the TNTZ alloy. Oxide film growth process of TNTZ is suppressed by the complex composition of the oxide layer that is spontaneously air-formed on its surface, at least for the material in the mirror-like polished state. Roughening of TNTZ surface by its chemical etching led to a rapid oxide layer growth in the PBS + H₂O₂, which was reflected by complete surface coverage with the oxide domes. *In situ* AFM experiments for the chemically activated materials indicate that the H₂O₂-induced growth of the oxide for TNTZ alloy follow the same mechanism as was found for CP-Ti.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Agata Sotniczuk: Writing – original draft, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Baojie Dou:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Investigation. **Yangping Liu:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Investigation. **Oumaïma Gharbi:** Methodology, Writing – review & editing. **Fan Sun:** Writing – review & editing, Resources. **Halina Garbacz:** Funding acquisition, Writing – review & editing. **Jeremy L. Gilbert:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Conceptualization. **Kevin Ogle:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

The raw/processed data required to reproduce these findings cannot be shared at this time as the data also forms part of an ongoing study.

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